

KASUO ISHIGURO’S CONTRIBUTION TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF WORLD LITERATURE

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Abstract. *In the dissertation, the problem of generations and the description of universal principles in the works of Kazuo Ishiguro, who is considered one of the most influential writers of the 21st century, and the example of the writer's famous works were scientifically approached. Kazuo Ishiguro, winner of the 2017 Nobel Prize in Literature, has been described as "a writer who, in his novels of great emotional power, exposes the void beneath our false attachment to the world." This dissertation contains quotations from the writer's works.*

Keywords: *songwriter, collaborative work, professional, success, spotted, publish, collection, writing fiction, consider, development, opportunities, to grow, develop in ways, influence, particularly, nominated, multiple times.*

Specific aspects of the development of British literature of the 20th-21st centuries. Christopher Banks, a well-known adventurer, has been tormented by the dream of knowing the reasons for the death of his parents since childhood, and finally, it will work. But this journey of Christopher, who set off from London to Shanghai at a very dangerous time, will be a journey from today’s reality to history, to the cruel realities of life.

Kazuo Ishiguro had not initially wanted to write fiction, wanting instead to become a songwriter. From the age of fifteen he would sit in his bedroom and write songs on his guitar. When he was thirteen he bought would-be 2016 Nobel Prize for Literature winner Bob Dylan’s album ‘John Wesley Harding’ and has said the record was a huge inspiration for him as it gave him the notion that words could be used in mysterious ways and that you could use them to create whole worlds. He was also inspired by the literature found in work from artists such as Leonard Cohen and Joni Mitchell. He considers his time writing songs as a teenager as his apprenticeship for becoming a fiction writer, and his songwriting soon turned into writing short stories.

Aged twenty-four, while having little professional success as a songwriter, he had a number of short stories published and was spotted by Faber & Faber in London, who remain his publisher today. He published his first novel ‘A Pale View of Hills’ in 1982 and has since published a short story collection and seven other novels, including *Remains of the Day* and *Never Let Me Go* which have both been adapted into award-winning films. Although writing fiction has become more of a priority for him, he still considers himself a songwriter and has written lyrics for a number of albums by singer Stacey Kent. He considers collaborative work to be an important part of his writing life. For him, working in another outlet with other artists stops his development from becoming static as it gives him opportunities to grow and develop in ways that he might not if he were to work alone, as writers may be prone to. He also cites films as a major influence on his work, particularly those from Japanese directors Yasujiro Ozu and Mikio Naruse.

Kazuo Ishiguro is a Japanese-born British novelist who won the Nobel Prize in Literature in 2017. He has been nominated for the “Booker Prize” multiple times, winning it for “*The Remains of the Day*” in 1989. He was only five when his parents moved to England, but had vivid images of an imaginary Japan around which he often builds his stories. His parents also

took the responsibility of making young Kazuo aware of his Japanese roots. While he has little familiarity with Japanese fiction, he was slightly influenced by the writings of Jun'ichiro Tanizaki, and to a greater extent by films by Yasujiro Ozu and Mikio Naruse. Most of his novels are set in the backdrop of World War II, and are marked by his almost lyrical description of regret fused with optimism. All his novels, except 'The Buried Giant', are narrated in the first-person style, and his protagonists often exhibit human failings. He has been very vocal about the political turmoil in the recent times, expressing his fears for Britain after Brexit, and in his Noble acceptance speech, he said that he hopes to create a “positive atmosphere at a very uncertain time” through his works.

Kazuo Ishiguro was born on November 8, 1954, in Nagasaki, Japan, to Shizuo Ishiguro and his wife Shizuko. He has an older sister, Fumiko, and a younger sister, Yoko.

He lived in a traditional Japanese house complete with sliding screens and tatami mats and decorated with heirlooms, samurai swords and banners. Three generations lived in Kazuo Ishiguro's home with his grandfather being the head of the family.

Kazuo Ishiguro's grandfather had spent time in Shanghai during the development of the textile machinery company 'Toyota'. Kazuo Ishiguro's father was born in Shanghai in 1920. His mother was living in Nagasaki during the time the US government dropped the atomic bomb in August 1945.

His father, who was a physical oceanographer, moved to Guildford, Surrey, in order to begin a two-year research project at the National Institute of Oceanography. When Kazuo Ishiguro was 15, his father turned down a post at a Tokyo university to stay in England, following which Kazuo Ishiguro formally became a British citizen in 1983.

He initially attended Stoughton Primary School and then got into Woking County Grammar School in Surrey. After finishing his school education in 1973, he travelled through the United States and Canada, and acted as a grouse beater for the Queen Mother in Balmoral.

In 1978, he completed his graduation from Kent University with a bachelor's degree in English and Philosophy. Two years later, he got his master's degree in Creative Writing from the University of East Anglia, where Malcolm Bradbury and Angela Carter were his classmates.

Three of Kazuo Ishiguro's short stories, “A Strange and Sometimes Sadness”, ‘Waiting for J’ and “Getting Poisoned”, were included in “Introduction 7: Stories by New Writers’ in 1981.

In 1982, he published his first novel, “A Pale View of Hills”. The story of Etsuko, a Japanese widow in England, who is trying to cope with her daughter's suicide, earned him the “Winifred Holtby Memorial Prize” in 1982.

In 1983, he published two short stories, “A Family Supper’ in 'Firebird 2: Writing Today’ and 'The Summer After the War’ in “Granta 7”. Another of his short stories, “October 1948” was published in “Granta 17” in 1985.

His second novel, “An Artist of the Floating World”, is set in post-World War II Japan and focuses on Masuji Ono who reflects on his past career as a political artist of imperialist propaganda. The book, released in 1986, was shortlisted for the “Booker Prize” and won the “Whitbread Book of the Year Award” that year.

In 1989, he bagged the “Man Booker Prize for Fiction” for “The Remains of the Day”, in which butler Stevens narrates in first person his professional and personal relationship with former colleague, housekeeper Miss Kenton. The novel was adapted into an eponymous film in 1993, starring Anthony Hopkins and Emma Thompson, which went on to win eight 'Academy Award' nominations.

His next novel, 'The Unconsoled' (1995), which describes the frustration of a famous pianist with his inability to take control of his commitments before a performance, marked a radical stylistic departure from his previous works. The book initially received overwhelmingly negative reviews for being “indecipherable”, but won the “Cheltenham Prize” that year and in 2006 was voted the third “best British, Irish, or Commonwealth novel from 1980 to 2005”.

He ventured into the detective novel genre with his fifth novel, “When We Were Orphans”, which was released in 2000. Despite the fact that it is considered one of his weakest works, a view he himself supports, the novel went on to win a nomination for “Man Booker Prize” that year. The next year, he published the short story “A Village After Dark” in “The New Yorker”.

In 2005, he released his sixth novel, “Never Let Me Go”, a dystopian science fiction novel which was adapted into a film in 2010 and a Japanese television drama in 2016. 'Time' magazine named it the best novel of the year and included it in “TIME 100 Best English-language Novels from 1923 to 2005”. The book was also shortlisted for the 2005 “Booker Prize”, the 2006 “Arthur C. Clarke Award” and the 2005 'National Book Critics Circle Award’.

In the following years, he wrote short stories like “Crooner”, “Come Rain or Come Shine”, “Malvern Hills”, “Nocturne” and “Cellists”, which were published in “Nocturnes: Five Stories of Music and Nightfall” in 2009.

His latest novel, 'The Buried Giant', released in 2015, is an existential fantasy tale set immediately after Arthurian Britain. The novel earned mixed reviews from critics.

Kazuo Ishiguro is also a screenplay writer who worked on two television films for Channel 4, “A Profile of Arthur J. Mason” and “The Gourmet” in 1984 and 1987 respectively. He was the original screenplay writer of the 2003 Canadian film “The Saddest Music in the World” and also wrote the 2005 drama film “The White Countess”.

In 2002, after he chose Stacey Kent’s “They Can’t Take That Away from Me’ for his “Desert Island Discs”, the jazz singer asked him to contribute lyrics to her album “Breakfast on the Morning Tram”. The album received Grammy nomination in 2009, following which he continued to write songs for her 2011 album, 'Dreamer in Concert', her 2013 album, 'The Changing Lights', and her 2017 album, “I Know I Dream”.

Kazuo Ishiguro’s most celebrated work so far is his third novel, 'The Remains of the Day’, which has been adapted into a film, a BBC radio program and a musical.

His 2005 novel, “Never Let Me Go”, has also earned him many awards and accolades, and was adapted into a film, a stage play and a TV show.

Kazuo Ishiguro received the Nobel Prize in Literature in 2017 for his illustrious literary career.

In 1989, he won the Man Booker Prize for his novel “The Remains of the Day”.

In 1982, he won the Winifred Holtby Memorial Prize for his novel “A Pale View of Hills”.

Kazuo Ishiguro met social worker Lorna MacDougall at the West London Cyrenians homelessness charity in Notting Hill while working as a residential resettlement worker there. They got married in 1986 and have a daughter named Naomi.

According to Kazuo Ishiguro, he is often surprised to think how generous his neighbors have been in a new country after the war. However, the only times he felt uncomfortable were while playing war games with friends, and often campaigned for fighting the Germans and not the Japanese.

In the life of Kazuo Ishiguro, who is considered one of the most influential writers of the world literature of the 21st century, the description of universal principles and the example of the writer's famous works are scientifically approached.

It led to the emergence of unique writers who presented their immortal and rare works to the literature of Britain and the world.

The Japanese writer tried to draw the attention of others to his tragic history and to create works of art describing the Second World War.

Kazuo Ishiguro's works of art are reflected in his themes, but show the tragedy of society, when society thinks about the future, remembers its past, cannot live with the past, otherwise a healthy society showed that it cannot be built.

Kazuo Ishiguro is one of the first echelons of the fast-moving literary train, and he has already proved that the Japanese can write better in English than the British.

Kazuo is one of the first echelons of the fast-moving literary train, and he has already proved that the Japanese can write better in English than the British. In fact, his language did not come out in English, he set foot on British soil at the age of five. At the same time, the author emphasizes that his works have a "universal" character that can be understood by any person. Indeed, the theme of Kazuo Ishiguro's works is mainly human. Adib describes universal problems and relationships in his works.

Undoubtedly, at the same time in the works of Kazuo Ishiguro

In the image of the heroes and the example of the time and space that surrounds them, it is possible to realize universal principles.

It is no exaggeration to say that Kazuo Ishiguro's works and his characters are still with us.

All of us are familiar with the universal feelings and worldview embodied in them. Kazuo Ishiguro's greatest achievement is that he understood these principles, penned them and continues to convey them to the reader.

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